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Earners of this certification have an in-depth understanding of how to use AWS services to implement data pipelines and to monitor, troubleshoot, and optimize cost and performance issues in accordance with best practices. Badge owners have technical expertise to understand the effects of volume, variety, and velocity on data ingestion. They are familiar with transformation, modeling, security, governance, privacy, schema design, and optimal data store design.

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